

Research

Security Risks Faced by Tajikistan and Its Impact on the “Silk Road Economic Belt Initiative”

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Accepted: 20 January, 2020; Online: 25 January, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3627740>

Abstract: *Tajikistan is currently actively promoting the implementation of “Silk Road Economic Belt Initiative” to stimulate the development of the nation’s economy, which has created a favorable trade cooperation environment for Tajikistan and China. Under the boosting of “Silk Road Economic Belt Initiative”, the two countries will hopefully form a comprehensive strategic cooperative partnership. Although Tajikistan’s economy and infrastructure to some extent lags behind other central Asian countries, it has abundant mineral and hydraulic resources that compensate for China’s deficiency in economic cooperation. Besides, Tajikistan has unique geographical and cultural environment that makes it the “outpost” in guarding regional security as well as the unstable factor in constructing “Silk Road Economic Belt Initiative”. For this reason, the analysis of the categories and causes of Tajikistan’s security risks plays an important role in promoting “Silk Road Economic Belt Initiative”. This essay attempts to study the cause of Tajikistan’s security risks and its influence on the implementation of “Silk Road Economic Belt Initiative” by sorting out Tajikistan’s risk types and their characteristics. “Silk Road Economic Belt Initiative” has an essential significance to both China and Tajikistan, and Tajikistan’s security and stability affect its operation and effects. Based on Barry Buzan’s security theory, this essay systematically analyzes Tajikistan’s security risks during 2014-2016 with the aim to add to the theoretical system of “Silk Road Economic Belt” and guarantee the efficient implementation of “Silk Road Economic Belt Initiative”.*

Keywords: *security risks; Tajikistan; Silk Road Economic Belt*

1.1 Background to the Study

China and Tajikistan established diplomatic relations in 1992. Over the 20 or so year, the bilateral relationship between China and Tajikistan has steadily developed. In 2011, the territory dispute between the two countries was settled. Two years later, China's General Secretary Xi Jinping proposed the strategic conception "the Belt and Road Initiative", which rendered central countries the important region in "Silk Road Economic Belt". Among them, Tajikistan actively responded to China's initiative, being the first country to sign the MOU (Memorandum of Understanding) of the "the Belt and Road Initiative" with China and established a cooperation council to support the implementation of the initiative. In September 2014, leaders of the two countries signed an agreement on deepening cooperation and established Sino-Tajikistan strategic partnership, further strengthening the two nations' bilateral relationship. Furthermore, China and Tajikistan have also deepened their cooperation in multiple fields including transportation, security, and culture and so on.

On the other hand, due to Tajikistan's weak national capacities and other external factors, the implementation and development of "the Belt and Road Initiative" are confronting various security risks. Firstly, Tajikistan is traditionally weak in military. Its domestic political situation is relatively stable for now, yet because of the distinct social structure Tajikistan has, conflicts between its local interest groups are prominent. In terms of economy, the improper economic structure in Tajikistan creates a frail financial environment which hinders the construction of infrastructure and improvement of living standard. To make things worse, corruption is pervasive in the nation, and ecological environment is fragile. The Tajikistan government is unable to handle those existing problems properly. Lastly, same as China, Tajikistan is facing the threats posed by the "Three Evil Forces", especially since 2014 when the global security situation has experienced drastic changes and the deterioration of Afghanistan's security status directly impacted Tajikistan's safety. And Tajikistan's security risks will in turn cause direct or indirect loss to "the Belt and Road Initiative" and affect the prospect of the "Economic Belt".

1.2 Statement of the Problem

This essay summarizes and analyzes the security risks facing Tajikistan based on comprehensive research on Tajikistan's status quo, then digs into the causes of these risks and finally comes up with solutions to eliminate them. Among them, the analysis of the risks and their causes is the most important part.

The difficult part of the study is the collection of literature and documents on Tajikistan security risks. Though there are a large number of materials, they are mostly scattered and random. Even so, in order to make the research results reliable and effective, it is necessary to collect as much information as possible through the Internet, library and surveys.

2. Definition of Key Concepts and Introduction to Theories

2.1 Definition of “Security”

Security is one of the most prominent issues human face, especially when security research has received growing attention in the international relation discipline since the Cold War becoming one of the most important research fields. Definition of security varies among different industries and scholars.

Realists’ understanding of security is based on power. Scholars such as Hans Morgenthau believe that power can not only reflect the basic strength structure in international system, but can also demonstrate the major motivation of actors. Realists tend to regard security as a derivative of power, which means that dominant actors naturally enjoy security. Consequently, they hold the view that power is the access to security. Pacifists, on the other hand, connect security with peace. The concept “peace” is conducive to historical inspect of security issues and can focus attention on the crucial subjects about “war”. Pacifists believe wars are the major threats to national security, and the solution to it is solving problems caused by wars. Idealists consider security as the result of peace and believe lasting peace could bring security to all countries.

In the middle and later periods of Cold War, international relations started to change. Security risks such as military threats and arm races gradually weakened while new research subjects in the international security field emerged and content of security research constantly expanded. At that time, security research started to attach more importance to economy, environment and human beings, which provoked concerns on “common security” and “comprehensive security”. Subsequently, feminism, post-structuralism, criticism, post-colonialism and many other schools all started their own research on security theories with different focuses.

The dictionary definition of security is: no danger (objective security), sense of security and no doubt (confidence in one’s own knowledge). Barry Buzan regards “security” as an effective tool to deal with national relations due to its penetration and resilience. The concept of “security” is widely used by researchers yet has no explicit definition.

Joseph Nye believes the concepts of security is complicated and have the function of promoting other values' instrumentality. Micheael H.H. Louw thinks that national security includes traditional defense policies and non-military national behaviors whose aim is to ensure nations' viability as political entities. Non-military national behaviors are the prerequisite for countries to exert influence and achieve their domestic and international goals.

2.2 Barry Buzan's Security Theory

Barry Buzan, professor of international relations in London School of Economics, is a representative of Copenhagen School. His research subjects include: concepts of international security and regional perspectives; international history and evolvement of international system since prehistory; international relation theory, especially structural realism. Professor Buzan has worked on security for more than 40 years, and his works give systematic introduction to research results of security.

Taking anarchy as the political background of his research, Buzan discusses security of human beings, nations and the whole world. Under the state of anarchy, nations are the primary main bodies, and operation mechanism of national security closely relates to interstate relations. The state of anarchy is also a dynamic balancing system full with competition. It cannot retain long-term security under the system of hegemony. In other words, security under the state of anarchy is relative.

Personal security is the smallest unit that the concept of security could apply to. It involves life, health, wealth and freedom. Personal security relates to yet contradicts with national security. A nation is the provider of security to individuals while is also the source of major threats (life threats, economic threats, power threats and social threats) to individuals. As Waltz once said, nation as well as individual's security level is inversely proportionate to freedom level. If one wants to obtain freedom, he or she has to take some kind of insecurity.

3. Security Risks in Tajikistan and Its Influence on the "Silk Road Economic Belt Initiative"

3.1 Military Risks

Tajikistan, located in the southeast of central Asia, borders on China, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan and Afghanistan. Borderlines of Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan cross in the Fergana Valley, making the place vulnerable to series conflicts.

Tajikistan and Uzbekistan have disputes and conflicts in many aspects. The relation between the two countries started to deteriorate after Tajikistan's civil war. Uzbekistan intervened

in Tajikistan's civil war out of its own security and interests, which aroused discontent from Tajikistan. Negative effects of the war consistently emerged and caused territory disputes between the two countries. In fact, the territory and border dispute between Tajikistan and Uzbekistan is a historical problem caused by the improper territory planning during the Soviet Union period. Although the two countries remain their original territory, rifts have since emerged and aggravated the crisis of the confidence between the two countries.

The competition for water resources further worsened the Tajikistan-Uzbekistan relation. In order to develop agriculture and guarantee electricity supply for economic growth, Rakhmon restarted the construction of Rogun Hydropower Station in 2008, which aroused fierce rebuke from Uzbekistan and in turn affected Uzbekistan's natural gas supply to Tajikistan. The Rakhmon government has been trying to build up the Rogun Hydropower Station even at the cost of suffering from military attacks from Uzbekistan. And problems caused by Rogun Hydropower Station are far beyond bilateral disputes. If the problem of water resources could not be solved timely, the relation between Tajikistan and Uzbekistan will continuously deteriorate.

Tajikistan passed the National Defense Law in 1995 which entitles president of the state to the supreme command of arm forces. It also stipulates that the Ministry of National Defense provide financial, technological and logistical supports for the army, and the General Staff conduct operational command of the armed forces. On October 3, 2005, Tajikistan passed National Military Doctrine, a military theory that places emphasis on defensiveness, trying to settle its internal and external security risks by joint effort from collective security treaty organization. In 2016, Rakhmon signed a military draft that stipulates Tajikistan conscript twice a year, converting the troops that have completed the conscription requirements into reserve forces. Since the Tajikistan authority worried that the opposite faction's strength would increase and its appeal in the security sector would expand, recruitment of contract soldiers has been suspended since 2000, impeding the improvement of Tajikistan army's cohesion and operational capability due to the lack of professional soldiers. Worse still, Tajikistan is short of experienced soldiers, and there are serious corruptions in the army.

Tajikistan has the weakest military capability among central Asian countries and is heavily dependent on foreign military resources and assistance. Currently, the major military risks Tajikistan facing are mainly from the nation's historical problems, such as its disputes and conflicts with Uzbekistan and its weakness in military forces. Central Asian countries are actively

promoting security cooperation to lessen military conflicts and reinforce regional stability, and therefore large-scale military confrontation might reduce in spite of occasional border conflicts. This offers an opportunity to establish a new regional security cooperation mode under the framework of the “Silk Road Economic Belt Initiative”.

3.2 Political Risks

“Strongman Politics” is one of the characteristics of central Asia politics. Because of the particular historical and cultural environment in this region, strongman politics plays a special role in development and stability of central Asian countries. After the collapse of Soviet Union, “strongmen” got on the political stage, gradually dragging central Asian countries from chaos to stability. Tajikistan Civil War broke out just after the collapse of Soviet Union, so strictly speaking, Rakhmon is not a political strongman. Nevertheless, the Rakhmon clan has become the largest political clan in Tajikistan by constitutional amendment and nomination. That is to say, Tajikistan is developing towards familial politics.

Rakhmon has 9 children in total, including 9 daughters and 2 sons. His eldest son Rustam Emomali was appointed as acting mayor of Tajikistan’s capital Dushanbe in 2017 who had been leader of National Center for Financial Regulation and Anti-corruption Agency formerly. His second daughter Ozoda took over the post of deputy foreign minister of Tajikistan in 2009. In January 2016, she was promoted to director of the Presidential Office. Her husband is the vice president of the State Bank.

Familial politics is typical of the “political atavism” phenomenon, a polity characterized by clans or families chronically controlling or influencing political systems. It manifests as the dominant status and special influence of clans in a political system. Social patterns influence political development. Familial politics is concentrated in Asia, especially in central Asia in recent years. From the prospects of history, culture, social formation and national development, familial politics, to some extent, could quickly collect resources for national reconstruction. After the Civil War, Tajikistan gradually enters a recovery period under the governance of the Rakhmon family and remains stable in its political environment, which is beneficial for Tajikistan’s long-term development.

However, familial politics has its intrinsic deficiency. First, legitimacy and orthodoxy of the successor will arouse conflicts within the family. Second, familial politics makes it easier for

family conflicts expand into public political areas thus triggering party splits. The Rakhmon family in Tajikistan not only controls the crucial political resources of the nation, but receives supports from Russia and inherits part of the political heritage left by Soviet Union. Therefore, the Rakhmon family's position is unshakable in the foreseeable future. Last and the foremost, the most eminent deficiency of familial politics is the "power economy". The political resources held by the Rakhmon family safeguard its control over the nation's economy and banking system. Power economy harbors corruption and that's why corruption is so pervasive in Tajikistan, not only in its economic sector but also in its security sector. Corruptive officials even trade with the outlaws and terrorists, and there is no efficient ways to eliminate corruption in Tajikistan, least for now.

Interest groups in Tajikistan are categorized by regions. Since the Soviet Union period, the division between north and south has widened. Due to its geographical environment and economic advantages, northern interest groups have obtained most of the political resources and have long held the leadership of the country. During the Soviet Union period, the Leninabad clique in the north has played an important role in the nation's crucial institutions. In contrast, the southern interest groups have long been on the political fringe. Tajikistan's Civil War is actually a competition between the northern and southern interest groups for national leadership. After the civil war, some oppositionists fled to Afghanistan while most of them returned to the south. The end of Civil War does not mean the resolution of disputes and conflicts among regional interest groups. The Tajikistan authority thinks that those opposition factions will cripple its governance, posing great threats to the country.

Up to now, the political environment in Tajikistan is generally stable and it's unlikely for Tajikistan to encounter political violence outburst in the short term. Governance of the Rakhmon family can not only provide a relatively stable political environment but also guarantee the consistency of policies hence reducing the cost of nation-building. However, regional interest conflicts still exist, especially the conflicts between the south and the central government. The Rakhmon government insists on implementing a centralized policy, which might arouse fierce resistance from regional forces. Under intervention of external factors, such kind of resistance would be dramatically amplified, undoubtedly causing political unrest, even wars. The construction of the "Belt Road Economic Belt" would thus be interrupted and the construction cost would increase.

3.3 Economic Risks

Due to the relatively small size of Tajikistan's domestic economy, the nation is heavily dependent on overseas remittances. Tajikistan's economy has begun to recover since 2011, resulting in improvement of its economic level and overall economic environment. During 2011 to 2013, Tajikistan maintained an economic growth rate of over 7%. However, western countries have imposed sanctions on Russia since 2014, which has also influenced Tajikistan who is heavily dependent on foreign currency. One year later, downward trend of Tajikistan's economy was rather obvious and its task of macro-economic construction was faced with unprecedented challenges. At the same time, its domestic consumption demand drastically shrunk and foreign trade volume declined. As a result, the nation's economic growth rate in 2016 declined rapidly to only 4%.

The second problem of Tajikistan's economy is the improper industrial structure. Service sector is the largest industry in Tajikistan and it mainly relies on remittances. Agriculture serves as the country's economic basis while industry is an important economic backbone. Yet the development speed of agriculture and industry is too slow to provide enough momentum for the upgrade of the nation's substantial economy.

Tajikistan is also facing a serious debt problem which impacts its financing capability. The nation's income and expenses are almost balanced even with some surplus sometimes. And the proportion of tax revenue in GDP is increasing year by year. But Tajikistan's debt paying ability is very limited and that's why it has a large amount of debt. By the end of 2015, the nation's foreign debts added up to 2.191 billion, accounting for 27.9% of the total GDP in that year. In 2016, that number reached 35.6%, almost hitting the "red line". China is Tajikistan's largest creditor nation and this kind of contractual relation between the two countries is likely to continue for some time given Tajikistan's current debt paying ability. What's worse, during the process of debt paying, new debts will be consistently created. If Tajikistan does not improve its economic capability promptly and continues to rely on external aid and remittances to support national economy, the "Silk Road Economic Belt Initiative" will be damped by various challenges and obstacles. Therefore, there is an urgent demand for Tajikistan to reform its economic structure and build up autonomy of economic development, reducing its reliance on foreign assistance. Otherwise, Tajikistan will eventually lose its economic independence, and the turbulence of foreign capital will slow down and even destroy Tajikistan's economy at any time, leading to collapse of efforts to implement the "Silk Road Economic Belt Initiative".

To make things worse, Tajikistan is in short of transportation and power infrastructures, and its relation with Uzbekistan is in a tension. Frequent natural disasters make lots of damages to the nation's already fragile and worn-out infrastructures, increasing cost of equipment maintenance, raw material supply and production sales. It is detrimental to Chinese enterprises and will impact the progress of constructing the "Economic Belt".

As Tajikistan has intrinsic deficiency in its infrastructure, investment from the "Silk Road Economic Belt Initiative" on Tajikistan yields little results. China as the biggest creditor country of Tajikistan invests constantly on it, yet Tajikistan's lack of debt paying ability resulting from economic dependence, huge amount of debt and years of financial deficit will impede the function the "Economic Belt Initiative" in the long run.

4. Causes of Tajikistan's Security Risks

4.1 Tajikistan's Intrinsic Defects

4.1.1 Social and Political Closure

There are many mountains and plateaus in Tajikistan and they are mostly in the south and east, which makes a natural separation between regions. In winter, with heavy snow sealing the mountain passes, it is even harder for different regions to communicate. Such kind of natural environment is beneficial to the survival of tribalism whereas detrimental to the prosperity of modern economy. Furthermore, the existing transportation system has not connected different parts of the nation, making it hard for cross-regional exchange. Drawbacks of infrastructure and transportation combined with influence from social structure and traditional culture, Tajik people's sense of region identification is far more intense than that of national identification.

Interest groups in Tajikistan often unit and divide their forces by region, forming political cliques with certain social influence. These cliques usually represent regional interests and play a crucial role in Tajikistan politics. The intense sense of tribal identification, to some extent, is in fact an extension of kinship and sibship in some certain regions, further complicating the relation network in the Tajikistan's society. Even the Tajikistan Civil War is ascribed to the tribal politics. The uneven distribution of the state power and the unbalanced development of regional economy generate a highly divisive localism in Tajikistan.

4.1.2 Social Conflicts

A latest *Industrial Development Report of the UN* lists Tajikistan with some of the poorest African countries, Afghanistan and North Korea as the world's low-income countries. According

Russia News Agency's survey of per capital GDP (in US dollars) of former Soviet Union countries, Tajikistan ranks the last among all the surveyed countries at \$2,749.

Economic backwardness and population explosion have caused phenomena of unfair distribution of income and lack of various resources. Not only that, economic problems are also the root of infrastructure deficiency in Tajikistan and trigger a series of social problems in employment, medical service and education.

A recent demographic statistics report from the Tajikistan Statistics Agency shows that Tajik population in 2019 reaches 9 million. Such a large population poses a huge challenge to the nation's environment and even social stability. In its mountainous areas adjacent to the border, there are many stateless people living under the condition of anarchy.

Teenagers take a large proportion of Tajik population, thus providing enough laborers to the society. However, Tajikistan's current economy could not generate sufficient jobs matching the number of workers, so a large number of workers have to go to Russia or Turkey to find jobs. But since the Russia economy shrinks, the Russian government introduced new regulations to raise the threshold for foreigners working in Russia in 2014, forcing a lot of Tajik workers going back to Tajikistan.

On the other hand, though Tajikistan has a large population, the literacy level of its citizens is generally low. Education investment in Tajikistan only shares a small proportion in its GDP, which causes a short in educational resources and in turn influences the cultivation of professional talents. Russia attracts a lot of high-quality talents from Tajikistan, making the brain drain even worse.

4.1.3 Deficiency of National Identification

The most famous political, economic and cultural centers in Tajikistan's history are Samarkand and Bukhara. They used to be divided into Uzbekistan during the Soviet Union period. The loss of the two cities leads to the missing of traditional cultural centers in Tajikistan and makes it harder for Tajik people to have a natural identification.

However, vacancy of cultural center aggregates tribal and regional identification and harbors regional interest groups. Consequently, civic awareness and cohesion in the country is so weak that it slows down the modernization of the country and hence influences the "nation building" process.

4.2 External Factors

4.2.1 Influence of Afghanistan's Security Situation

Afghanistan's terrorist activities gradually transferred from south to north in 2014 and 2015, posing a serious threat to central Asian countries. Three fifths of the battles between Afghanistan military and Taliban happened near the Tajikistan-Afghanistan border.

Since 2014, frequent terrorist activities and chaos on the northern border of Afghanistan greatly impacted trade flows between Tajikistan and Afghanistan.

On August 21, 2016, Taliban blew up the Aullch Bridge in Kunduz Province which is the main land access connecting Tajikistan and Afghanistan. The 300-meter-long bridge links Afghanistan's northern provinces with Afghanistan's border town and also the trade hub of central Asia—Shehan. The Ishkashim market and Khorugh market in the northern Afghanistan closed right after the arrival of Taliban, and bilateral trade volume between Tajikistan and Afghanistan declined by 60% within 3 months.

4.2.2 Intervention of External Forces

Tajikistan has always been an important country for Russia to defense against western forces including the U.S. and served as an essential fortress for central countries to resist western penetration. Traditionally, central Asian countries are within the influence sphere of Russia, and the Putin government pays great attention to controlling of central Asia affairs. Tajikistan is one of the central Asian countries that Russia has been paying attention to and Tajikistan's weakness in military and dependence on Russia's economy make the country vulnerable to Russia's influence or even control.

After years of development, Uzbekistan's economic and military strength have improved while its global position has barely promoted. Uzbekistan is ambitious about expanding its international influence, which contradicts with Russia's interests. The conflicts between Uzbekistan and Russia will inevitably cause damages to small countries in central Asia, especially Tajikistan.

4.2.3 Improvement of Tajikistan's Security Environment

As the social transformation progresses slowly in Tajikistan, various problems have emerged. If Tajikistan wants to enjoy the profits from the "Silk Road Economic Belt Initiative", it is imperative for the country speed up its reform. The Tajikistan government is seeking to make wholesome and practical long-term plans for the country. By learning from previous experience and listening to people's aspirations and demands, the government has evaluated the country's

existing resources and opportunities, predicted internal and external factors influencing political and economic environment and eventually clarified that the primary task for the Tajikistan government in the next 15 years is to improve the living standard of people. The aim of this plan is to make full use of electricity to solve transportation problems and ensure food security and quality, finally creating productive employment.

Based on the above plan, Tajikistan formulated a “Development Plan of 2020-2030”. This short-term plan has two main tasks: the first the one is to enhance efficiency of substantial economic sectors, promoting industrial diversification and boosting competitiveness of national economy; another is the development of human capitals, mainly achieved by investing more on education and medical service to improve the overall literacy level of citizens. Meanwhile, the government is committed to improving employment productivity and labor market quality with the aim to reduce unemployment.

5. Suggestions for Implementing the “Silk Road Economic Belt Initiative” in Tajikistan

To ensure the efficient and proper functioning of the initiative, governments’ supports and investment are indispensable both from China and Tajikistan. The “Silk Road Economic Belt Initiative” is a significant development strategy which needs consistent national backup.

Tajikistan is weak in its national strength and falls far behind other CISs. Therefore, construction and implementation of the “Economic Belt Initiative” mainly rely on China’s investment. Such kind of international initiatives require a large amount of investment at the beginning and have a relatively long output circle, which means that the Chinese government needs to constantly provide capitals and resources for it. To lessen pressure on the Chinese government, Tajikistan is supposed to actively participate in the cooperation with China and gradually increase its investment on the initiative.

In terms of political factors, with the changes in Afghanistan’s internal and external environment, the decline of Russia’s international status and upgrading of superpower games among central Asian countries, geopolitical layout is more favorable to Tajikistan. However, Russia’s influence on Tajikistan cannot be belittled. One of the solutions to alleviate Russia’s control over Tajikistan is to further exploit the effects of the “Silk Road Economic Belt Initiative” and “Eurasian Economic Union”.

China and Tajikistan could also increase bilateral cultural activities to strive for non-governmental supports for the initiative. Trust and supports from people are essential for the

implementation of the initiative and can offset losses caused by regime changes to some extent. Educational and cultural cooperation between China and Tajikistan could produce more talents who can provide professional knowledge for the understanding and operation of the initiative.

Previously, China's investment in Tajikistan under the "Economic Belt Initiative" is mainly focused on infrastructure, industrial production and transportation, with only a little going to direct social assistance. This will limit Tajikistan citizens' perception of the benefits brought by the initiative. China should accordingly change its investment pattern to help Tajikistan solve more practical problems. On the one hand, the government should promote publicity of the initiative to intensify people's support for it and stimulate their longing for happy and stable life. On the other hand, the government needs to increase medical aid to solve the medical care problem in Tajikistan; improve sanitary conditions, especially cleansing of water resources.

5. Conclusion

Tajikistan's security risks do not exist and arise independently, and all aspects of security risks are intertwined. Tajikistan's natural environment, to a certain extent, limits the mode of economic development. The isolation of the environment and the fragility of the economy are the main causes of Tajik tribal politics and regional politics.

The "Silk Road Economic Belt Initiative" will encounter various risks in countries along the route. At present, Tajikistan's economic and social security risks pose the greatest challenge to it. However, despite all those risks, mutual understanding between countries along the "Economic Belt" and sufficient support from governmental and non-governmental organizations will promise a bright future for the initiative.

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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